

FOSTERING A CULTURE OF QUALITY: PILOTING SELF-ASSESSMENT IN UZBEKISTAN'S VET INSTITUTIONS

Odilov Asliddin Akhmatjonovich

*O'zbekistondagi kasb-hunar ta'limi islohotlarini qo'llab-quvvatlash loyihasi (VET4UZ),
Helvetas Swiss Intercooperation sifat kafolati bo'yicha bosh mutaxassis¹,*

E-mail: odilov.asliddin@helvetas.org

Xolboyev Jamshid Abduxaliqovich

Ipak Yo'li Turizm va Madaniy Meros Xalqaro Universiteti Professional ta'lim bo'limi boshlig'i

E-mail: koshiy32@gmail.com

Abstract. This paper examines the implementation of a pilot self-assessment initiative within Uzbekistan's VET sector, conducted through the Swiss-supported VET4UZ project. This paper analyzes the initiative's design, implementation strategy, early insights, and implications for scaling nationwide.

Keywords: vocational education and training, quality assurance, self-assessment, institutional capacity building, hospitality training

СОЗДАНИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ КАЧЕСТВА: ПИЛОТИРОВАНИЕ САМООЦЕНКИ В УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация. Статья вносит вклад в понимание того, как страны с переходной экономикой могут эффективно реформировать системы обеспечения качества ПОО, одновременно формируя устойчивый внутренний потенциал. Также статья анализирует структуру инициативы, стратегию реализации, первые выводы и возможные пути масштабирования на национальном уровне самооценки в учреждениях ПОО.

Ключевые слова: профессиональное образование и обучение, обеспечение качества, самооценка, развитие институционального потенциала, подготовка кадров в сфере гостеприимства.

SIFAT MADANIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: O'ZBEKISTONNING KASB-HUNAR TA'LIMI MUASSASALARIDA O'Z-O'ZINI BAHOLASHNI SINOVDAN O'TKAZISH

Annotatsiya. Maqola o'tish davri iqtisodiyotiga ega mamlakatlar barqaror ichki salohiyatni shakllantirish bilan bir vaqtda, kasb-hunar ta'limi sifatini ta'minlash tizimlarini qanday samarali isloh qilishlari mumkinligini tushunishga hissa qo'shadi. Shuningdek, maqolada kasb-hunar ta'limi muassasalarida o'zini o'zi baholashning tashabbusi tuzilmasi, uni amalga oshirish strategiyasi, dastlabki xulosalar va milliy miqyosda kengaytirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: kasb-hunar ta'limi, sifatni ta'minlash, o'z-o'zini baholash, institutsional salohiyatni oshirish, mehmondo'stlik sohasida tayyorlash.

Uzbekistan is currently undergoing a significant economic transformation from a public sector-dominated economy to one increasingly driven by private enterprise. This transition creates new demands for a responsive VET system that aligns with evolving labor market needs. Since 2019, Uzbekistan has introduced substantial reforms to its VET system, establishing a three-level

¹ Senior Quality Assurance Expert, Support to VET Reforms Project in Uzbekistan (VET4UZ), Helvetas Swiss Intercooperation

professional training structure, introducing new quality assurance frameworks and a national qualifications framework.

However, as identified through a comprehensive Capacity Needs Assessment (CNA) conducted in March 2023, these reform efforts have encountered implementation challenges, particularly in shifting from a historically centralized, compliance-oriented quality control approach toward a more modern quality assurance system that balances accountability with enhancement. As a result, in October 2024 government reforms consolidated all VET institutions under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation (MHESI) and transformed the previously fragmented three-tier VET system into unified institutions (technicums). While these structural changes improve governance efficiency, the CNA identified a critical gap: the omission of comprehensive Quality Assurance (QA) mechanisms poses significant risks to the value of awarded qualifications.

The Swiss-funded VET4UZ project (2021-2025) supports this reform agenda by working to strengthen VET governance, quality assurance systems, teacher training, and economic actor participation. This paper examines a key component: the piloting of self-assessment processes in ten VET institutions specializing in hospitality education, aiming to establish self-assessment as a cornerstone for building robust internal quality assurance and developing a culture of continuous improvement.

1. Theoretical Framework and Context

1.1. Current State of VET Quality Assurance in Uzbekistan

The CNA revealed that Uzbekistan's quality assurance system remains in transition from a Soviet-era top-down control system toward a more modern approach. The current system is characterized by high centralization with multiple actors involved at different levels, external quality assessment primarily focused on compliance with state educational standards, limited stakeholder involvement (particularly from employers and students), and internal quality assurance processes that primarily mirror external requirements rather than addressing institutional priorities.

As the CNA report noted: "VET institutions still do not feel an ownership of their IQA" (Odilov, 2023). This lack of ownership presents a significant barrier to developing a genuine culture of quality and continuous improvement.

The transition from compliance-based to improvement-focused quality systems requires substantial cultural and organizational shifts. Massy (2003) argues that effective quality assurance must balance external accountability with internal improvement mechanisms to create sustainable change. This balance is particularly challenging in centralized systems where institutions have historically had limited autonomy.

1.2. Necessary Paradigm Shifts

The CNA identified several necessary paradigm shifts in conceptualizing quality:

From	To
Viewing quality as absolute and fixed	Understanding quality as relative, multi-layered, and evolving

Applying a single dominant standard	Recognizing multiple aspects of quality assessment
Provider-determined quality	Quality based on stakeholders' needs
Focusing on final product	Emphasizing service processes (there are procedures and processes in place to ensure the desired quality, and to make learning outcomes labour market relevant)
Quality controlled by a specialized unit	Quality as everyone's responsibility

These shifts represent a fundamental change in how quality is understood and approached within the VET system, moving from a compliance-oriented to an enhancement-oriented mindset.

1.3. Self-Assessment as Foundation for Quality Culture

Research supports the role of self-assessment as a critical foundation for developing quality culture within educational institutions. Cedefop (2015) identifies self-assessment as a primary mechanism for developing institutional ownership of quality, noting that effective quality assurance systems must combine external accountability with internal improvement processes.

Visscher (2009) found that when properly implemented, self-assessment contributes to enhanced organizational learning capacities, improved data-driven decision making, greater staff engagement, more effective resource allocation, and stronger alignment between institutional mission and practices.

In VET contexts specifically, Odilov (2024) found that self-assessment processes help bridge the gap between labor market needs and educational delivery by creating systematic feedback mechanisms that involve stakeholders in quality improvement. Visscher (2009) demonstrated that VET institutions with mature self-assessment practices were more successful in adapting to changing economic demands and technological developments.

2. Research Methodology and Pilot Design

2.1 Research Approach and Selection of Hospitality Sector

This study employs a mixed-methods action research approach utilizing document analysis, interviews, observations, and assessment of institutional capacity. The hospitality sector was strategically chosen based on its economic significance, critical skills shortages, strong employer commitment, comprehensive sectoral coverage of all ten relevant VET institutions, and high demonstration potential.

2.2 Implementation Strategy and Capacity Development

The implementation model consists of three interconnected tiers:

Tier 1: Pioneer Institutions — Four VET institutions testing and refining the self-assessment framework

Tier 2: Sector-Specific Expansion — Six additional institutions ensuring a comprehensive approach

Tier 3: National Expert Development — A pool of experts supporting implementation and enabling nationwide scale-up

Overberg (2019) notes that quality initiatives often face challenges when they are perceived as bureaucratic impositions rather than meaningful improvement tools, suggesting that implementation approaches must actively engage stakeholders in practical applications. To overcome this implementation challenge, capacity building employs **project-based learning** rather than traditional training, addressing participants' lack of essential soft skills (self-reflection,

critical thinking, teamwork, communication) that previously hindered implementation. This approach features learning-by-doing, manageable learning segments, alternating theory and practice, and ongoing coaching between formal sessions.

3. Implementation Strategy

3.1. Phased Implementation Approach

The implementation follows a carefully structured roadmap from March to December 2025:

Preparation Phase (March-April 2025)

- Project kick-off meeting
- Training of QA task force
- Finalization of QA standards and self-assessment toolkit

Self-Evaluation Training and Implementation (May-November 2025)

- Three training workshops focusing on different aspects of self-assessment
- Coaching between workshops to support implementation
- Peer-learning workshops to share challenges and best practices
- Mid-project review to refine subsequent phases

Report Development and Validation (July-December 2025)

- Writing of draft and final self-evaluation reports
- Development of Quality Improvement Plans (QIPs)
- Validation workshop with Ministry and employers
- Dissemination conference to share results

3.2. Support Mechanisms

The implementation includes multiple support mechanisms:

- Regular coaching sessions between formal workshops
- Facilitated peer learning circles for sharing challenges and solutions
- Multiple draft reviews with feedback on self-evaluation reports
- Expert consultation from national and international experts
- Digital support platform for sharing resources and facilitating communication

4. Early Implementation Insights and Discussion

4.1. Changing Institutional Perspectives on Quality

Initial training sessions have begun to shift institutional perspectives on quality. Baseline assessment data revealed that prior to the initiative, 82% of participants associated quality primarily with compliance and inspection. After the first training phase, 67% of participants had developed a more nuanced understanding of quality as a tool for institutional improvement.

4.2. Balancing Technical and Soft Skills Development

Initial observations indicate that participants particularly value the soft skills components, with 78% rating these elements as "highly useful" in feedback surveys. The integration of soft skills development appears to be enhancing participants' confidence in implementing self-assessment.

4.3. Challenges in Building Self-Reflection Capacity

Building capacity for critical self-reflection presents a significant challenge, particularly in a system that has historically focused on compliance. Some institutions struggle with defensive responses to identifying weaknesses, mirroring what Overberg (2019) describes as 'quality abracadabra' — resistance strategies employed when quality management is seen as disconnected from core educational values.

4.4. Key Success Factors and Challenges

A critical success factor is finding an appropriate balance between standardization (to ensure consistency) and institutional ownership (to foster genuine engagement). The approach of providing a standardized toolkit while encouraging institutions to adapt processes to their specific context addresses this balance.

Other key challenges include:

- Building sustainable quality leadership within institutions
- Creating authentic rather than compliance-driven self-assessment
- Successfully integrating self-assessment with external quality assurance systems

5. Conclusion and Implications

The self-assessment initiative contributes to Uzbekistan's broader economic transition by establishing quality assurance mechanisms that align human capital development with economic needs. By developing these capacities in the hospitality sector initially, the project establishes a model that can be extended to other priority sectors as economic diversification continues.

Evidence from international studies suggests that robust quality assurance systems in VET have direct positive impacts on graduate employment outcomes. The VET4UZ initiative has significant potential to enhance labor market outcomes by ensuring VET programs develop both technical competencies and soft skills, building systematic feedback loops between labor market needs and program design, and creating mechanisms for continual adaptation of training.

Based on early implementation experiences, recommendations for future phases include:

1. Strengthening the connection between internal and external quality assurance
2. Deepening employer engagement beyond curriculum development
3. Developing institutional capacity for data-driven decision-making
4. Establishing sustainable support mechanisms beyond the project period
5. Documenting and sharing institutional transformation journeys
6. Aligning self-assessment with the emerging National Qualifications Framework
7. Integrating quality indicators with labor market information systems

This study contributes to understanding how transitional economies can effectively reform VET quality systems while building sustainable internal capacity. While focused on Uzbekistan's context, the findings offer valuable insights for other countries undertaking similar transitions in their vocational education systems.

References

1. Cedefop. (2015). Handbook for VET providers: Supporting internal quality management and quality culture. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
2. Massy, W. (2003). Honoring the Trust: Quality and Cost Containment in Higher Education. Bolton, MA: Anker Publishing 2003.
3. Odilov, A. (2023). Assessment of capacity needs of key stakeholders in quality assurance in VET. Swiss project "Support to VET reforms in Uzbekistan", available at <https://tvet.edu.uz/upload/iblock/206/81ozdyi70pm2m9ovkh3w2scwmd7qax45.pdf>
4. Odilov, A. (2024). Quality Assurance Handbook: Supporting the development of internal and external quality assurance in VET. Swiss project "Support to VET reforms in Uzbekistan", available at <https://tvet.edu.uz/upload/iblock/f73/sf6s3pd0xlb75oeetukuvqq446g1ilbz.pdf>
5. Overberg, J. (2019). 'Skipping the quality abracadabra': academic resistance to quality management in Finnish higher education institutions and quality managers' strategies to

handle it. *Quality in Higher Education*, 25(3), 227–244.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2019.1685656>

6. Visscher, A. J. (2009). *Improving Quality Assurance in European Vocational Education and Training: Factors Influencing the Use of Quality Assurance Findings*. Dordrecht: Springer.